

The EC focus on Responsible R&I as leverage for P2P-production

From the perspective of complex flow systems P2P-production can be considered a resilient practice emerging in response to (multi-faceted) crises that indicate the limits (and likely collapse) of the current system. However, since this system is strongly institutionalised whereas the emergent alternatives are not, the latter risk getting recuperated within (key aspects of) the old system. Especially the capitalist economic, legal and governance models often do not offer the manoeuvring space for alternatives to break through. It is therefore crucial for P2P-practices to increase their ascendancy by fostering the development of adapted economic and legal frameworks. A potential strong leverage for this could be found in the current emphasis on 'Responsible R&I' by the EC. RRI as a concept was launched to address the big challenges of today. However, just as P2-practices are at risk of recuperation in the capitalist system, RRI-projects too often are approached as just another box to tick for getting access to research funds, yet without getting embedded into a new paradigm. The question is therefore under what conditions RRI could become a leverage for P2P production.

In this paper I propose a commons oriented framework for RRI - based on a systemic approach of the current crises - clarifying the role of R&I in addressing these crises and the conditions (lock-ins and leverages) that allow RRI-projects to bring about alternatives. The aim is to clarify *how* RRI can become a leverage for fostering commons-oriented alternatives for the capitalist model and increasing the resilience of our societies. A *transformation of the R&I-system* is needed both in terms of content and process. In terms of **content** mainstream R&I mostly focuses on technical innovations (new products or processes) that are then implemented in society following the capitalist conception of production and consumption (with a view to growth of private profit). Even 'sustainable' innovations (e.g. aiming at decoupling) are still embedded in the market mechanism for their uptake, so the overall result remains extractive (increasing entropy). RRI therefore focuses on *broader systemic innovations* aiming at common wellbeing rather than private profit. In terms of **process** mainstream R&I is conceived as an exclusive domain of the expert, with the rest of society as the consumer (or the object) of knowledge. RRI democratises the process, making *science a common endeavour* in which 'indigenous' and expert knowledge are considered equal.

This approach of RRI implies a paradigm shift; yet most researchers and R&I institutions function within 'normal' science without conscious reflection on (the validity of) the paradigm they use. So **specific infrastructure** is required as an intermediary between the established R&I system and emergent 'commons based' innovators. How this infrastructure is to be designed and ran is currently being studied (by H2o2o-project FoTRRIS). Its aim is to develop, test and validate a design (including a charter/mandate, a methodology and a value creation model) that allows the RRI-hubs to be commons based themselves. In conclusion we will **formulate some policy recommendations**.

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